

VETERINARY SCIENCES

MORPHOLOGICAL BLOOD PARAMETERS OF TURKEYS DURING ACUTE AND CHRONIC HISTOMONOSIS

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Abstract

The study aimed to evaluate morphological blood parameters in turkeys with acute (50-day-old) and chronic (120-day-old) histomonosis (n=16). In the acute course, a decrease in hemoglobin (−2.6%) and erythrocytes (−3.0%) was observed, accompanied by pronounced leukocytosis (+24.5%). The leukogram revealed an increase in eosinophils (+23.8%) and band neutrophils (+105.3%), indicating a left shift. The leukocyte intoxication index (LII) increased to 0.93 (+52.5%). In the chronic course, more pronounced anemia was detected, with hemoglobin decreasing by 15.8% and erythrocytes by 7.6%. Leukocytosis was less marked (+13.0%), but eosinophilia (+50%) and a decrease in segmented neutrophils (−9.7%) were recorded. LII reached 0.79 (+25.4%). The results indicate that morphological blood parameters are informative markers for assessing the severity and stage of histomonosis in turkeys.

Keywords: turkeys, histomonosis, hematology, leukogram, leukocyte intoxication index

Introduction

Protozoan invasions in poultry cause lesions of the intestine and liver and are accompanied by pronounced changes in hematological parameters [1, 2]. Under modern intensive poultry farming conditions, these diseases remain one of the leading causes of decreased productivity and reduced flock survival [3].

Turkey poults in early ontogenesis are exposed to numerous stress factors, including inadequate nutrition, improper housing conditions, bacterial infections, as well as helminth and protozoan invasions. These factors lead to reduced natural resistance of the organism and suppression of the hematopoietic function of the bone marrow [4]. Stress is known to be one of the key factors negatively affecting the immunobiological reactivity of animals and poultry [5], while parasitic invasions caused by helminths and protozoa act as immunosuppressive agents, contributing to the development of immunodeficiency states and increasing susceptibility to infectious diseases [6].

The immune system is considered an integrated complex of cellular and humoral components, including lymphocytes, plasma cells, and macrophages, which provide complex protective reactions of the organism. Its functioning is mediated through specific immune mechanisms involving antibodies and sensitized cells, as well as through nonspecific

mechanisms implemented by various cellular and physiological systems [7, 8].

In the intestinal mucosa, *Eimeria* spp. and *Histomonas meleagridis* release metabolites that exert toxic effects on turkey tissues and suppress both cellular and humoral components of the immune system. In mixed invasions, disturbances of both specific and nonspecific immune responses are observed, contributing to the generalization of the pathological process [9]. Chronic parasitic diseases, in turn, lead to profound disorders of the hematopoietic, antioxidant, and immune systems, which are associated with the toxic effects of parasite metabolites and metabolic alterations [10].

Reduced functional activity of the immune system in poultry leads to increased susceptibility to diseases, decreased viability, and lower productivity. In this context, blood investigation becomes particularly important as one of the most informative biological substrates [11].

Blood is a key component of the internal environment of the organism, ensuring the maintenance of homeostasis, while at the same time being highly dynamic and sensitive to physiological and pathological changes [12, 13]. Its clinical and diagnostic significance is обусловated by its continuous interaction with organs and tissues, which enables the reflection of internal physiological and pathological processes through qualitative and

quantitative changes in hematological parameters [14, 15].

According to the literature, histomonosis in turkeys is associated with significant biochemical and hematological disorders, including decreased albumin levels and increased globulin concentrations [16].

Similar hematological alterations have also been described in mixed protozoan invasions. In partridges infected with *Histomonas* spp. and *Tetratrichomonas*, pronounced leukocytosis accompanied by increased numbers of neutrophils, lymphocytes, monocytes, eosinophils, and basophils was observed, indicating an intensive inflammatory and parasitic response of the organism. Hemogram analysis revealed a significant increase in leukocyte counts (by 165.8%; 49.87 ± 7.82), neutrophils (by 617.9%; 9.62 ± 3.41), lymphocytes (by 156.4%), as well as monocytes and eosinophils ($P < 0.05$). At the same time, a decrease in hemoglobin levels (-26.9%) and erythrocyte counts (-19.2%) was recorded compared to clinically healthy birds. Basophil levels also tended to moderately increase (+16.0%) [17].

It is well known that eosinophilia is a characteristic feature of parasitic invasions and allergic reactions [18, 19]. In poultry affected by histomonosis, increased numbers of monocytes/macrophages and decreased heterophils in peripheral blood have also been reported, which is explained by their migration to inflammatory lesions [20].

The immune response plays an important role in the pathogenesis of histomonosis. It has been demonstrated that an effective local immune response in the intestine can limit parasite dissemination, whereas insufficient immune protection contributes to the generalization of the pathological process. In turkeys, an increased number of lymphocytes, particularly cytotoxic T cells, has been observed in the ceca, indicating the involvement of immunopathological mechanisms in disease development [21].

Clinical and laboratory studies indicate that anemia, leukocytosis, leukocyte formula shift, and alterations in liver enzymes (AST, LDH) may serve as indicators of severe histomonosis and associated complications [22]. At the same time, the course of infection largely depends on the bird species; in turkeys, histomonosis is characterized by a more severe course compared to chickens, which is associated with differences in immune responses [23].

It has been established that cellular immunity plays a leading role in protection against *Histomonas meleagridis*, whereas the humoral response is considered less significant. Moreover, turkeys develop a less effective early local immune response in the intestine, which contributes to the development of severe forms of the disease [24].

The relevance of morphological blood studies is determined by their high informative value for assessing the functional state of the poultry organism, early diagnosis of pathological processes, and evaluation of the severity of parasitic diseases, particularly histomonosis.

The aim of the study was to determine the characteristics of morphological blood parameters in turkeys with acute and chronic histomonosis.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted at the Laboratory of Epizootology, Animal Disease Monitoring and Providing of the Odessa Research Station of the National Scientific Center "Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine" (NSC "IECVM"). The experimental group consisted of 16 turkeys, including 8 birds aged 50 days with acute histomonosis and 8 birds aged 120 days with chronic histomonosis. Clinical signs of the acute (intestinal) form included diarrhea and depression, whereas the chronic (hepatic) form was characterized by anemia, emaciation, feed refusal, and cyanosis in the head region. The diagnosis was finally confirmed by pathological and anatomical examination.

For morphological studies, blood samples (2–3 mL) were collected from turkeys after slaughter using sterile syringes and subsequently used for hematological analysis.

Morphological blood parameters were determined using conventional hematological methods (Kondrakhin et al., 1985). Erythrocyte counts and hemoglobin concentration were measured photometrically using a FEC-M photocolormeter according to the method of Havrylets (1966), while leukocyte counts were determined using a Goryaev counting chamber (Chumachenko, 1991). The leukogram was evaluated by differential counting of leukocyte types in fixed blood smears stained according to Romanowsky–Giemsa. In addition, hemoglobin concentration was assessed using the hemoglobin cyanide method (Derviz & Vorobyov, 1959).

Blood smears were also examined to determine the proportion of erythrocytes with signs of toxic granulation, and the leukocyte intoxication index (LII) was calculated according to the method of Sarykov and Kushch (1985) using formula (1).

Leukocyte Intoxication Index (LII):

$$LII = \frac{(4 \times My + 3 \times Ju + 2 \times Ba + Se) \times (Pl + 1)}{(Mo + Ly) \times (Eo + 1)} \quad (1)$$

My – myelocytes;

Ju – juvenile neutrophils;

Ba – band neutrophils;

Se – segmented neutrophils;

Pl – plasma cells;

Mo – monocytes;

Ly – lymphocytes;

Eo – eosinophils.

The animal experiments conducted in this study complied with the current legislation of Ukraine (Article 26 of the Law of Ukraine No. 5456-VI of 16 October 2012 "On Protection of Animals from Cruel Treatment"), the "General Ethical Principles for Animal Experiments" adopted by the First National Congress on Bioethics (Kyiv, 2001), and international bioethical standards, including the provisions of the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes (Strasbourg, 1985) [25, 26].

Research results. In 50-day-old turkeys with acute histomonosis, a significant decrease ($p < 0.001$)

in hemoglobin concentration by 2.6% (98.5 ± 0.5 g/L) (101.1 \pm 0.3 g/L), due to a 3.0% reduction in erythrocyte count (Table 1).

Table 1.

Morphological blood parameters of 50-day-old turkeys with acute histomonosis (n = 8, M \pm m)			
Parameters	Experimental group	Control group	% of control
Hemoglobin, g/L	101.1 \pm 0.3	98.5 \pm 0.5***	-2.6
Erythrocytes, T/L	30.1 \pm 0.1	29.2 \pm 0.2***	-3.0
Leukocytes, G/L	30.6 \pm 0.1	38.1 \pm 0.1***	+24.5
Leukogram, %			
Basophils	0.5 \pm 0.1	-	-
Eosinophils	2.1 \pm 0.2	2.6 \pm 0.8*	+23.8
Juvenile neutrophils	0.5 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.1*	-40.0
Band neutrophils	1.9 \pm 0.2	3.9 \pm 1.0*	+105.3
Segmented neutrophils	34.1 \pm 1.9	32.6 \pm 1.2*	-4.4
Lymphocyte	56.3 \pm 2.9	57.2 \pm 0.9***	+1.6
Monocyte	4.6 \pm 0.2	3.4 \pm 0.1*	-26.1
Leukocyte intoxication index	0.61	0.93	+52.5

Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 compared with the control group

In the experimental group of turkeys, a significant increase (p < 0.001) in leukocyte count by 24.5% (38.1 ± 0.1 G/L) was recorded compared to 30.6 ± 0.1 G/L in the control group. The leukogram revealed a significant increase (p < 0.05) in eosinophil count by 23.8% ($2.6 \pm 0.8\%$) compared to $2.1 \pm 0.2\%$ in clinically healthy turkeys. The number of band neutrophils in infected turkeys significantly increased (p < 0.05) by 105.3% and reached $3.9 \pm 1.0\%$ versus $1.9 \pm 0.2\%$ in the control group. These findings indicate a severe course of the intestinal form of histomonosis. The left shift of leukocytes suggests destruction of intestinal tissue, allowing the parasite to penetrate blood vessels and reach the liver through the portal vein, thereby contributing to the transition of the disease into a chronic form. A significant decrease (p < 0.05) in

monocyte count by 26.1% ($3.4 \pm 0.1\%$) compared to $4.6 \pm 0.2\%$ in the control group was also recorded, indicating immunosuppression and the development of aplastic anemia.

In clinically healthy turkeys, the leukocyte intoxication index (LII) was 0.61 conventional units, whereas in infected birds it reached 0.93 conventional units, which was 52.5% higher. An increase in LII indicates progression of the disease toward a chronic stage.

Investigation of morphological blood parameters in turkeys with chronic histomonosis revealed a significant decrease (p < 0.001) in hemoglobin concentration by 15.8%, reaching 96.8 ± 0.9 g/L compared to 115.0 ± 0.5 g/L in clinically healthy birds (Table 2).

Table 2.

Morphological blood parameters of 120-day-old turkeys with chronic histomonosis (n = 8, M \pm m)			
Parameters	Control group	Experimental group	% of control
Hemoglobin, g/L	115.0 \pm 0.5	96.8 \pm 0.9***	-15.8
Erythrocytes, T/L	29.1 \pm 0.1	26.9 \pm 0.2***	-7.6
Leukocytes, G/L	32.3 \pm 0.3	36.5 \pm 0.5***	+13.0
Leukogram, %			
Basophils	0.5 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.1*	-40.0
Eosinophils	1.6 \pm 0.1	2.4 \pm 0.2**	+50.0
Juvenile neutrophils	0.5 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.1	-
Band neutrophils	1.8 \pm 0.2	3.6 \pm 0.1***	+100.0
Segmented neutrophils	32.0 \pm 1.1	28.9 \pm 0.5*	-9.7
Lymphocytes	59.9 \pm 1.2	61.2 \pm 0.9*	+2.2
Monocytes	3.7 \pm 0.5	3.1 \pm 0.9*	-16.2
Leukocyte intoxication index	0.63	0.79	+25.4

Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 compared with the control group

A decrease in erythrocyte count by 7.6% (26.9 ± 0.2 T/L) compared to 29.1 ± 0.1 T/L in the control group was also recorded. Reduced hemoglobin concentration and erythrocyte count indicate the development of anemia and chronic inflammatory processes in infected birds.

The leukocyte count increased by 13.0% and reached 36.5 ± 0.5 G/L compared to 32.3 ± 0.3 G/L in the control group. An increase in eosinophils by 50%

also indicates the presence of an inflammatory process in turkeys with the chronic hepatic form of histomonosis.

The proportion of segmented neutrophils in healthy turkeys was $32.0 \pm 1.1\%$, whereas in infected birds it decreased to $28.9 \pm 0.5\%$, which was 9.7% lower (p < 0.05), indicating suppression of the immune response.

The leukocyte intoxication index (LII) in the control group of turkeys was 0.63 conventional units, whereas in birds with chronic histomonosis it reached 0.79 conventional units, representing an increase of 25.4%. However, compared to the acute course of the disease, this value was 15.1% lower.

Conclusions

1. Histomonosis in turkeys is accompanied by pronounced alterations in morphological blood parameters, the nature and intensity of which depend on the form and course of the disease. The acute course is characterized by the development of moderate anemia, pronounced leukocytosis, a left shift of the leukocyte formula, increased eosinophil counts, and elevated leukocyte intoxication index, indicating an active inflammatory process and a high level of endogenous intoxication.

2. In chronic histomonosis, more profound disturbances of the erythrocyte component of blood were observed, manifested by decreased hemoglobin levels and erythrocyte counts, indicating the development of anemia. At the same time, leukocytosis was less pronounced; however, eosinophilia, leukocyte formula shift, and increased leukocyte intoxication index persisted, reflecting a prolonged inflammatory process and immunological exhaustion of the organism.

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